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AN ITERATION METHOD FOR MAPPINGS OF UNIFORMLY ACCRETIVE TYPE IN L_p -SPACES

We establish an iteration method which is useful for determining the solution of equations $Ax = b$ with mappings of uniformly accretive and uniformly continuous type in L_p or l_p -spaces with $p \geq 2$. The succession is built by $x_{n+1} := x_n - c_n J^{-1}(Ax_n - b)$.

1. INTRODUCTION

Now let X be a Banach space, X^* the dual space; A a (possibly) nonlinear mapping of X into X^* ; for $f \in X^*$ and $x \in X$ denote $f(x) = \langle f, x \rangle$ the generalized duality pairing.

DEFINITION 1. The mapping J denote the duality mapping from X to 2^{X^*} . J is given by

$$Jx = \{f^* \in X^* : \|f^*\|_*^2 = \|x\|^2 = \langle x, f^* \rangle\}.$$

If X^* is strictly convex, then J is single-valued, and if X^* is uniformly convex, then J is uniformly continuous on bounded sets (see [1]). Thus, by a single-valued normalized duality mapping, we shall mean a mapping $j: X \rightarrow X^*$ such that for each u in X , $j(u)$ is an element of X^* which satisfies the following two conditions:

$$\langle j(u), u \rangle = \|u\|^2, \quad \|j(u)\|_* = \|u\|.$$

(a) The mapping $A: X \rightarrow X^*$ is said to be accretive if and only if for each $x, y \in D(A)$ there is some $j \in J(x-y)$ such that

$$\langle Ax - Ay, j \rangle \geq 0.$$

(b) The mapping A is said to be uniformly accretive if there exists a real, positive, increasing function $m(t)$, $m(t) \rightarrow \infty$ for $t \rightarrow \infty$, such that for each $x, y \in D(A)$ there is some $j \in J(x, y)$ such that

$$\langle Ax - Ay, j \rangle \geq m(\|x - y\|).$$

(c) A is said to be strongly accretive if and only if $m(t) = mt^2$ ($m > 0$ is said to be the constant of accretiveness).

(d) A is said to be coercive if and only if:

$$\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle Ax, x \rangle}{\|x\|} = 0.$$

2. A CONVERGENCE THEOREM FOR REAL SEQUENCES

THEOREM 1. Suppose (t_n) is a real sequence with:

$$(1) \quad t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - c_n g(t_n) + c_n^2 h(t_n).$$

For $0 < t < \infty$, $g(t)$ and $h(t)$ are positive and continuous functions. Further we suppose:

$$(2) \quad c_n > 0, \quad c_n \rightarrow 0, \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c_n = \infty,$$

$$(3) \quad h(t) = O(g(t)) \text{ for } t \rightarrow \infty.$$

Then the sequence (t_n) converges to zero.

PROOF. We subdivide the proof to several steps.

1. Assertion: (t_n) is a bounded sequence. If (t_n) is an unbounded sequence then there exists a partial sequence $t_{n'} \rightarrow \infty$. From (1) follows:

$$t_{n'}^2 - c_{n'} g(t_{n'}) + c_{n'}^2 h(t_{n'}) > t_{n'}^2.$$

In view of the fact that $c_{n'} > 0$ we get:

$$\frac{h(t_{n'})}{g(t_{n'})} > \frac{1}{c_{n'}} \text{ with } t_{n'} \rightarrow \infty.$$

Because of $c_{n'} \rightarrow 0$ we obtain a contradiction to (3).

In the following let be $k = \sup(t_n)$.

2. Assertion: $\lim t_n = 0$. Assuming that $t_n \geq d > 0$ for all n . Now we set

$$(4) \quad c := \min \frac{g(t)}{h(t)} \text{ for } d \leq t \leq k.$$

According to the premise is $c > 0$. Because of $c_n \rightarrow 0$ there exists an integer N so that $2c_n < c$ for $n > N$. In accordance with (1) and we obtain for $n > N$:

$$(5) \quad t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - c_n g(t_n) + 0.5 c_n g(t_n) = t_n^2 - 0.5 c_n g(t_n).$$

Now we consider the function $g_1(t) := \inf_{t \leq \tau \leq k} [\min(\tau, g(\tau))]$. This function $g_1(t)$ has the following properties:

$$(6) \quad 0 < g_1(t) \leq t \quad \text{for } 0 < t \leq k,$$

$$(7) \quad g_1(t) \leq g(t),$$

$$(8) \quad g_1(t) \text{ is an increasing function.}$$

From (5) and (7) it follows that:

$$(9) \quad t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - 0.5 c_n g_1(t_n) \quad \text{and} \quad 0.5 c_n \leq (t_n^2 - t_{n+1}^2) / g_1(t_n).$$

Since $g_1(t) > 0$ for $t > 0$, the sequence (t_n) is decreasing. $1/g_1(t)$ is also decreasing. If $G_1(t) = 1/g_1(t)$ then:

$$G_1(t_n^2) - G_1(t_{n+1}^2) = \int_{t_{n+1}^2}^{t_n^2} 1/g_1(t^2) dt \geq (t_n^2 - t_{n+1}^2) / g_1(t_n^2).$$

Therefore we have

$$G_1(t_n^2) \leq G_1(t_0^2) - 0.5 \sum_{i=0}^n c_i.$$

By use of the properties (6) and (8) and the divergence of (c_n) we obtain:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} t_n = 0,$$

but this is a contradiction to $t_n \geq d > 0$.

1. Assertion: $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} t_n = 0$. Without limitation of generality we assume:

$$(10) \quad \lim_{h(t) \rightarrow 0} \frac{g(t)}{h(t)} = 0 \quad \text{for } t \rightarrow 0.$$

Otherwise we reduce $g(t)$, so that (10) is fulfilled and (2) stays valid.

Let be:

$$(11) \quad m(\varepsilon) := \sup\{t \in [0, k]: g(t)/h(t) \leq \varepsilon\} \quad \text{for } 0 < \varepsilon \leq k.$$

Because of (10), $m(\varepsilon)$ is well defined. Obviously $m(\varepsilon)$ is a monotone function. It follows that there exist a limit

$$a := \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} m(\varepsilon) \geq 0.$$

From the continuity of $g(t)$ and $h(t)$ it follows:

$$\frac{g(a)}{h(a)} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{g(m(\varepsilon))}{h(m(\varepsilon))} \leq \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \varepsilon = 0,$$

i. e. $g(a) = 0$ therefore is $a = 0$.

Let be $\varepsilon > 0$. Now we choose N such that:

$$(12) \quad c_n < \varepsilon \text{ for } n > N$$

and

$$(13) \quad t_N^2 < \varepsilon^2 M + m^2(\varepsilon)$$

with $M = \max h(t)$ for $0 \leq t \leq k$. Because of $c_n \rightarrow 0$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} t_n = 0$ exist such a N . By means of the method of complete induction we show that:

$$(14) \quad t_n^2 < \varepsilon^2 M + m^2(\varepsilon) \text{ for } n \geq N.$$

On account of (13) the relation (14) is correctly for $n = N$. Let be (14) correctly for $n \geq N$. According to (5) we get:

$$(15) \quad t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - c_n [g(t_n) - c_n h(t_n)].$$

If $g(t_n) - c_n h(t_n) \leq 0$ then we get on account of (12) the relation

$$(16) \quad \frac{g(t_n)}{h(t_n)} \leq c_n < \varepsilon.$$

In accordance with (11) it follows that $t_n \leq m(\varepsilon)$ and we obtain

$$t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 + c_n^2 h(t_n) \leq m^2(\varepsilon) + \varepsilon^2 \cdot M.$$

But if $g(t_n) - c_n h(t_n) > 0$ we get from (15) also

$$t_{n+1}^2 < t_n^2 \leq m^2(\varepsilon) + \varepsilon^2 M.$$

Therefore (14) is proved. From $m(\varepsilon) \rightarrow 0$, for $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and from relation (14) follow that:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (t_n) = 0.$$

q. e. d.

3. CONVERGENCE THEOREM

The next inequality we need to prove our theorem in L_p see [1, Lemma 1].

THEOREM 2. Let be $X = L_p$ or l_p (with $p \geq 2$). The following inequality holds for all $x, y \in X$

$$(17) \quad \|x - y\|^2 \leq (p - 1)\|x\|^2 + \|y\|^2 - 2\langle x, j(y) \rangle.$$

Now we consider again the equation $Ax = b$, $A: X \rightarrow X^*$ for $X = L_p$ or l_p ($p \geq 2$).

THEOREM 3. Suppose, the mapping A is a uniformly accretive and uniformly continuous (with $M^2(t) = O(m(t))$) and (c_n) is a real sequence with:

$$c_n > 0, \quad c_n \rightarrow 0, \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c_n = \infty.$$

Then, the succession $x_{n+1} := x_n - c_n J^{-1}(Ax_n - b)$ (J is the duality mapping) converges to some solution x^* of $Ax = b$.

PROOF. 1. The existence of a solution follow from a theorem by Deimling (see [2]).

2. Convergence. For $Ax^* = b$ holds:

$$x_{n+1} - x^* = x_n - x^* - c_n J^{-1}(Ax_n - Ax^*).$$

We set $B = J^{-1}A$ and get

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_{n+1} - x^*\|^2 &\leq \|x_n - x^*\|^2 - 2c_n \langle Bx_n - Bx^*, j(x_n - x^*) \rangle + \\ &\quad + (p - 1)c_n^2 \|Bx_n - Bx^*\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

The hypothesis yields:

$$\langle Bx_n - Bx^*, j(x_n - x^*) \rangle = \langle Ax_n - Ax^*, j(x_n - x^*) \rangle \geq m(\|x_n - x^*\|)$$

and from $\|J^{-1}\| = 1$ it follows that

$$\|Bx_n - Bx^*\| \leq \|Ax_n - Ax^*\| \leq M(\|x_n - x^*\|).$$

We set $t_n := \|x_n - x^*\|$ and in consideration of the previous two relations we obtain:

$$t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - 2c_n m(t_n) + c_n^2 (p - 1) M^2(t_n).$$

Theorem 2 yields: $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x^*\| = 0$, q.e.d.

EXAMPLE 1 (A strongly accretive and lipschitzian). For $m(t) = mt^2$, $M(t) = Mt$ ($m, M > 0$) we get: $c_n = m/M^2$. The mapping $Tx = x - (m/M^2)J^{-1}(Ax-b)$ is a contraction (see [3]). In case of Hilbert space we have the statement of the Lemma of Browder and Petryshyn.

EXAMPLE 2 (A strongly accretive and hölder-continuous). For $m(t) = mt^2$ and $M(t) = Mt^\alpha$ ($0 < \alpha < 1$) we obtain:

$$c_n = m M^{-2/\alpha} \|Ax_n - b\|^{\frac{2}{\alpha}-2}$$

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